

**GRAPHITE/EPOXY BOOMS FOR THE SPACE SHUTTLE
REMOTE MANIPULATOR**

D. R. Dunbar and A. R. Robertson
General Dynamics Convair Division
San Diego, California

R. Kerrison
SPAR Aerospace Products Ltd.
Toronto, Ontario

Abstract

The Space Shuttle remote manipulator system (RMS) consists of two adjoining arm booms. One end of this 50-foot assembly is attached to the Shuttle and the other end to a grapple mechanism. The weight, stiffness, and strength requirements of the manipulator led to the selection of graphite/epoxy for the booms. In this paper, the design, manufacture, and assembly of the booms are discussed to demonstrate how design requirements were met.

This 20-foot long graphite/epoxy tube makes one segment of the RMS arm boom assembly.

Introduction

The RMS is being designed, built, and tested in Canada under the direction of the National Research Council of Canada and the NASA Lyndon B. Johnson Space Center in Houston, Texas. Prime contractor for the RMS is SPAR Aerospace Products Ltd., Toronto, Canada. The RMS, Figure 1, is part of the payload handling system of the Shuttle and includes the hardware installed in the payload bay and crew compartment and the support software. The payload bay hardware consists of four major assemblies: mechanical arm assembly, standard end effector (the payload grappling mechanism), thermal-protection system, and the closed-circuit television system.

Prime subcontractor for the arm booms is General Dynamics Convair Division of San Diego, California. In December 1976, General Dynamics initiated a program to design, fabricate, test, and deliver one set of qualification arm booms and two sets of flight arm booms. The arm booms are part of the mechanical arm assembly, Figure 2; the arm assembly is the largest in the RMS, measuring 50 feet in length and weighing 830 pounds. During launch, the arm assembly is firmly attached to the Orbiter at several locations by retention latches. These are released just before the arms are extended in orbit and are reattached after use and before reentry and landing.

Along with weight, overall arm stiffness is an important design driver for the RMS. Stiffness is critical from the standpoints of control system stability and operator acceptability. Other design parameters include emissivity, thermal conductivity, impact damage tolerance, alignment tolerances, and stiffness and strength after fatigue cycling. A discussion of the detailed design follows.

Fig. 1 — The remote manipulator system (RMS) forms a key element in the Shuttle Orbiter payload handling systems.

Fig. 2 — The RMS mechanical arm assembly consists of two 18-foot long graphite/epoxy arm booms connected to six pivot points.

Development Phase

During the Development Phase (completed in September 1977), a unique design, Figure 3, evolved from a unique set of requirements.

REQUIREMENT	DESIGN BASELINE
High stiffness & stability	Ultra-high modulus GY-70/934 graphite/epoxy
Damage resistance	Bumper of Kevlar/epoxy over honeycomb core
Fracture control	Laminate with ability to arrest cracks
Lightweight	Thin-walled tube with intermediate stabilizing rings

Materials used on the arm booms were selected for their ability to satisfy the specified requirements. Each element of the design was considered separately, and materials were evaluated functionally.

The tube assemblies, the primary structural elements in the arm booms, contribute the greatest weight and are stiffness critical. Ultra-high modulus GY-70/934 graphite/epoxy by Fiberite was chosen because it meets the stiffness and strength requirements within the weight constraints and because it is relatively durable with an inherent ability to blunt and stop cracks under moderate stress levels. Rockwell International uses the Fiberite resin for the Orbiter cargo bay doors, and General Dynamics uses it for the Nimbus-G and Seasat-A antennas. GY-70/934 was again the logical choice for the internal stiffener rings, which are stiffness critical. Because of the mechanical fasteners that secure the end rings to the graphite/epoxy tubes, the doubler build-ups at the tube ends have more of a strength than stiffness requirement. To provide the toughness needed, T-300 fibers are combined with the 934 resin in the properly oriented build-up.

The 2124-T851 aluminum alloy was selected as the end ring material for next assembly bolting because it has a higher and more reliable triaxial fatigue strength than the graphite/epoxy composite, has high corrosion cracking resistance, has guaranteed short transverse properties, is approved for Space Shuttle applications, and is extremely stable after machining from plate.

Design Approach

For both upper and lower arm booms, the ply orientation and thickness of the graphite-epoxy seamless tube were determined to meet strength, stiffness, and damage tolerance requirements at minimum weight. The total weight allowed for the two booms is 108 pounds; the current design weighs 106.8 pounds. For a complete weight breakdown, see Table 1.

Fig. 3 — The arm boom design is a lightweight yet durable tubular member constructed of GY-70/934 graphite/epoxy.

Table 1. Manipulator arm booms current weight summary.

Item	Specification Weight (lb)	Current Weight (lb)
Upper Boom	(56.1)	(54.4)
Tube	39.8	39.3
Energy Absorption	5.3	7.7
End Rings	3.0	3.7
Splice Rings	0.9	0.0
Internal Rings	2.1	1.2
Cable Provisions	2.8	1.8
Fasteners, Adhesive & Misc	1.1	0.7
Contingency	1.1	0.0
Lower Boom	(51.9)	(52.4)
Tube	30.6	31.2
Energy Absorption	6.1	9.1
End Rings	3.0	3.7
Splice Rings	0.9	0.0
Internal Rings	2.1	2.0
Cable Provisions	3.2	2.0
CCTV Camera Provisions	3.7	3.7
Fasteners, Adhesive & Misc	1.2	0.7
Contingency	1.1	0.0
TOTAL	108.0	106.8

Tube Design – Since the basic tube is a stiffness-critical thin shell, ultra-high modulus GY-70/934 was selected; the resulting lamina properties are given in Table 2. Laminates were designed with the help of computer optimization to meet requirements at minimum weight. All stiffness requirements were met with these laminates, as shown in Table 3. Strength requirements were also met with no excessively large margins, indicating a balanced design.

Table 2. GY-70/934 properties used in the analysis.

$E_{11} = 40.7 \times 10^6$ PSI	$t = 0.005$ IN./PLY
$E_{22} = 0.95 \times 10^6$ PSI	$CTE_{11} = -0.51 \times 10^{-6}$ $\mu\epsilon/F$
$\nu_{12} = 0.30$	$CTE_{22} = 16.0 \times 10^{-6}$ $\mu\epsilon/F$
$G_{12} = 0.95 \times 10^6$ PSI	$\epsilon_{11tu} = 0.0014$
$\rho = 0.063$ LB/IN. ³	$\epsilon_{11cu} = 0.0015$

Table 3. Arm stiffness requirements were met.

	UPPER ARM					
	ID = 12.86 IN.	OD = 13.01 IN.				
	LOWER ARM					
	ID = 12.86 IN.	OD = 12.96 IN.				
	I (IN. ⁴)	J (IN. ⁴)	EI CALC (10 ⁹ LB-IN. ²)	EI REQ (10 ⁹ LB-IN. ²)	GJ CALC (10 ⁹ LB-IN. ²)	GJ REQ (10 ⁹ LB-IN. ²)
UPPER ARM	63.74	127.48	1.42	1.40	0.72	0.70
LOWER ARM	42.25	84.50	0.84	0.83	0.53	0.42

To maintain stability of the thin-walled tube, intermediate rings, Figure 4, are spaced along the length of the tube. Spacing is set using a nonlinear Brazier-effect collapse analysis that implements the computer code STAGSC, Figure 5. The rings prevent Brazier's effect (which can flatten the tube under bending, leading to premature collapse of the tube wall and reduced effective bending stiffness), and they prevent acoustic fatigue problems by increasing the frequency of vibration of the sidewall to well above high-energy acoustic levels.

End Rings – To maximize fatigue strength, a bolted end joint, Figure 6, was designed; the clevis ring puts titanium HiLoc pins in double shear. High strength T300/934 graphite/epoxy is used to build the tube wall thickness locally for added strength.

Bumper Shell – The basic thin-walled tube is subject to many forms of damage on the ground and in space. For example, on the ground the arm could be bumped when installed in the Orbiter or smashed by small tools dropped by technicians working in the area. In space, the arm could be bumped against payloads or against the Orbiter sill during stowage, or it could be hit by meteorites. Because of such threats, an impact requirement of five foot-pounds was set, and an energy absorbing bumper system, Figure 7, was developed to meet the requirement.

Fig. 4 – Molded intermediate rings prevent ovalation due to Brazier effect.

Fig. 5 – STAGSC model used for Brazier effect collapse analysis.

Fig. 6 – Bolted end ring joint was designed for fatigue strength.

Fig. 7 – The bumper shell absorbs impact energy by crushing a Kevlar-49 covered honeycomb outer layer.

Test Program

A summary of the most significant structural tests is given in Table 4. Tests relating to thermal performance (emissivity, thermal conductivity, and thermal expansion) and flammability were also conducted. A discussion of the five of the more technically significant tests follows.

1. Laminate Fatigue Tests after Thermal Cycling – These tests were designed to verify that thermal cycling of laminate specimens does not degrade the fatigue life or residual strength of the selected laminates below design values. Two GY70/934 graphite epoxy panels were fabricated, one with the upper-arm laminate and one with the lower-arm laminate. Nine one-inch by nine-inch specimens of each laminate were machined from each panel and thermally cycled as follows:

- Run three cycles (one cycle ran 10 minutes at +232F, 10 minutes at room temperature, and 10 minutes at -250F), and then count, measure, and map microcracks on the edges of three control specimens.
- Repeat (a) but use 10 cycles.
- Repeat (b) until there is no increase in the quantity or size of the microcracks resulting from thermal cycling.

Table 4. Summary of development phase tests.

	LAMINATE FATIGUE TESTS AFTER THERMAL CYCLING	END JOINT FATIGUE LIFE WITH THERMAL CYCLING	DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF PROTECTION SYSTEM		FRACTURE CONTROL & CRACK GROWTH	ACOUSTIC
			SCREENING	VERIFICATION		DAMPING FACTOR
DATA MEASUREMENT	• CYCLES TO FAILURE (OR RESIDUAL STRENGTH FOR RUNOUTS)	• CYCLE & RESIDUAL STRENGTH	• C-SCAN ON UNDATED & DAMAGED ARTICLES	• C-SCAN ON UNDATED & DAMAGED ARTICLES • RESIDUAL STRENGTH	• CYCLE & RESIDUAL STRENGTH	• DAMPING FACTORS
PARAMETERS	• 2 LAMINATES • 2 REPETITIONS	• 1 JOINT DESIGN • 2 REPETITIONS • 2 LAMINATES	• 1 LAMINATE • 7 PROTECTION SYSTEMS • MULTIPLE IMPACTS	• 2 LAMINATES • 1 PROTECTION SYSTEM • 8 IMPACTS/SPECIMEN • 3 TEMPERATURES	• 2 LAMINATES	• 1 LAMINATE (TRANSVERSE) • 1 LAMINATE (LONGITUDINAL) • 1 AMPLITUDE DECAY CYCLE
TOTAL NO. OF SPECIMENS	4	4	7	2	10	4

After 43 cycles, microcracking and propagation of existing microcracks ceased. Tabs were then bonded on each end, and specimens were fatigue cycled at loads equivalent to or considerably above the qualification load levels. If failure had not occurred after 2,500,000 cycles, the test was terminated, and the specimens were statically tension tested to failure. When testing continued over a weekend, runout exceeded 2,500,000 cycles. All fatigue tests were conducted at an R-value (minimum stress-maximum stress) of ~1.0; results are shown in Figure 8. The results indicate that failure would not occur at limit stress levels of 11.3 and 11.9 ksi for the upper and lower arm boom laminates. Even fatigue loading at ultimate stress levels of 19.1 and 22.0 psi for the upper and lower arm boom laminates would not result in premature failure.

2. Damage Tolerance of Protective System – The purpose of these tests was to verify that the selected bumper could protect the load-carrying graphite epoxy tubes from damage at the design impact level of five foot-pounds. These tests were conducted in two stages: 1) preliminary study to screen various candidate bumper systems, and 2) critical evaluation of one selected system.

Although the results of preproposal testing of the HRP honeycomb and Kevlar skin design were encouraging, it offered only one data point out of enumerable possibilities. Therefore, a more objective approach was thought to be essential if an optimum design from cost, function and weight aspects was to be developed. Candidate bumper protection systems were developed from past experience in materials technology and from experience with vendors related to this design problem. Four candidate bumper protection systems were evaluated in the screening program.

HRH-10 Nomex honeycomb precrushed to a 0.15 to 0.20 inch height to minimize shock levels through the core into the laminate.

HFT bia weave (Fibertruss) honeycomb uncrushed at a uniform thickness of 0.15 inch. Two core sizes, 1/8 and 3/16, were evaluated to determine the effect of core sizes.

5052 aluminum alloy honeycomb in 1/8 cell at 3.1 density. This material was considered because of its capability in energy impact designs.

Corrugated Kevlar, a non-honeycomb material that can easily conform to the cylindrical shape of the boom. Moreover, the longitudinal corrugations provide additional strength to the boom.

Each of these panels had a one-ply 102 Kevlar fabric skin on the outer surfaces. The Kevlar skin is adhesive bonded to the corrugation or honeycomb, and this subassembly is then adhesive bonded to the graphite/epoxy tube. EA934 adhesive is used to bond all interfaces.

The specimen geometry selected was an arc segment with a 12.9-inch radius, 16 inches wide across the arc and 26 inches long. These panels were constructed on a 30-inch long half-cylinder aluminum tool. The thin walled graphite/epoxy laminate was selected for the test panels because it was expected to be more susceptible to impact damage. The impact tests were conducted using two-inch diameter, flat-ended steel to deliver five ft-lb impacts. In initial tests, impacts were made normal to the specimen surface, but in subsequent tests, impacts were made on

Fig. 8 - S-N curves for thermally cycled GY70/934 specimens.

selected specimens at various oblique angles, see Figure 9. The range of impact velocities is shown in Table 5. The specimens were inspected by radiograph and by ultrasonic C-scanning before and after testing.

Results of these screening tests led to the selection of HRH-10-3/16-3 precrushed honeycomb core with a one-ply 102 Kevlar-49/934 fabric outer skin. The core and skin were bonded to the sample with EA 934 adhesive. Full diameter verification sections were then prepared for test. The damage protection verification specimens, Figure 10, were impacted with the four-pound, two-inch diameter steel dropped 15 inches to strike the specimen at a spot 30 degrees from the centerline.

Minimal damage on the lower-arm specimen and no damage on the upper-arm specimen resulted from one impact; very slight damage occurred from the other two impacts. After the protection system was machined off, both specimens were tested to failure in compression. Failures occurred above design loads in an acceptable manner.

3. Fracture Control and Flaw Growth - Adequate flaw growth life and residual strength of damaged or flawed arm booms were demonstrated in these tests. Two sources of damage were identified: cracks or flaws originating during manufacturing, and cracks or flaws resulting from impacts occurring at any time. Damaged or flawed structure must withstand qualification level fatigue loads and then have enough residual strength to withstand qualification level strength-stability loads.

Fig. 9 – Impact test procedure.

Table 5. Five foot-pound impact test conditions.

Condition	Weight of Impactor (lb)	Distance Impactor Dropped (In.)	Impact Velocity (ft/sec)
1	0.25	240	35
2	0.5	120	25
3	1	60	18
4	5	12	8
5	8	7.5	6.3

Fig. 10 – Damage protection verification specimens with bumper system in place.

MIL-A-83444 defines damage tolerance design requirements, including initial flaw sizes and locations, for metallic airplanes. Although this specification does not apply directly to composite structures, the basic guidelines regarding structural types, inspection levels, and initial flaw assumptions were used in the development and verification of damage-tolerant composite arm booms. A basic premise of MIL-A-83444 is that initial crack-like flaws may exist anywhere in a structure, and that these flaws will stabilize under cyclic tensile loads and eventually will reach a critical length; at this point, the structure no longer has adequate residual strength to carry some specified required tensile loads.

Crack growth seldom occurs in graphite/epoxy structures. However, cyclic loads can cause delaminations to increase in size, thereby degrading the strength of the part. Of all failure modes, compressive stability likely suffers the most; therefore, development testing addresses this potential problem.

As evident from this discussion, qualification of the arm booms for damage tolerance was primarily on the basis of tests rather than analysis. Initial flaws due to manufacturing defects are assumed to escape detection and to exist in the structure when it enters service. Damage due to impacts is assumed to occur at any time and is therefore regarded as initial flaws existing in the structure when it enters service. The screw driver impact, a possible threat itself, is added to simulate meteoroid damage.

The fracture control test program required 10 specimens, configured as shown in Figure 11.

The upper-arm specimen graphite/epoxy shell was not damaged by the impactor, but the lower-arm specimen was damaged as shown in Figure 12. As expected, the screw driver penetrated the graphite/epoxy shell of both specimens, see Figure 13.

All upper and lower arm specimens survived the 800 blocks of spectrum loading and were statically tested. Failure of the specimens during static testing occurred at levels between 1.5 and 3.2 times ultimate load.

4. End Joint Fatigue Life with Superimposed Thermal Cycling — In these tests, end-joint fatigue life was verified with superimposed thermal cycling. Specimens were the same as used in the fracture control program but were one-third the width.

Fig. 11 — Fracture control test specimen.

Fig. 12 – Defect 2I – lower arm specimen impact from two-inch diameter steel impactor, weighing four pounds, dropped from 15 inches striking at a 30-degree angle.

Fig. 13 – Defect 3I – upper arm specimen after 20-foot screw driver drop at 90-degree angle.

Several specimens were subjected to a corrosive salt spray environment before testing to demonstrate the corrosion-resistant characteristics of the end joint design. In the arm boom design, thermal stresses in the aluminum-to-composite joint are minimized by using mechanical fasteners, and fatigue life is enhanced by eliminating adhesive joints. EA934 adhesive is present in the joint area only as a liquid shim. Bonding of the joint is prevented by using 0.001-inch thick teflon on the O.D and I.D of the tube at each end in the joint area.

Examination of specimens following 120 hours of salt spray testing revealed no evidence of corrosion. All test specimens survived the 800 blocks of spectrum loading with superimposed thermal cycling and were statically tested in tension to failure, which occurred at levels between 1.5 and 2.7 times ultimate load. Since exposed specimens failed at higher loads than the unexposed specimens, salt spray exposure seemed to have no detrimental effect.

5. Flammability – A bumper protection system specimen was submitted to NASA, Johnson Space Flight Center, for flammability testing. Upward propagation configuration flammability tests were conducted on the test specimen in an air atmosphere at 14.7 psia using a Cleanweld Type-B igniter placed in a 20-gage (AWG) nichrome wire coil. After the test article was supported in the test figure, an igniter was positioned approximately 1/4-inch below the convex surface, as depicted in Figure 14.

Fig. 14 — Flammability test configuration.

The mounted test configuration was installed in the test chamber. The chamber was sealed, evacuated, and backfilled by partial pressure additions of oxygen and nitrogen to produce the specified 14.7 psia air test environment. The test specimen was soaked in the test environment for three minutes before the monitoring instrumentation and igniter power supply were activated. After test completion, test instrumentation was secured, the test chamber was vented to atmospheric pressure (approximately 12.4 psia at WSTF), and the specimen was removed for post-test inspection. The material burned with an orange flame and then self-extinguished. The elliptically-shaped burn was 3.5 inches in length by 2.5 inches in width; burn time was 29.2 seconds.

Some smoke was observed, but no sparks or soot. Further, no mass transfer occurred but small quantities of black, brittle, flexible fibrous residues remained after testing, see Figure 15.

Flammability regulations require that materials be self-extinguishing within six inches of the igniter in the worst-case environment. This requirement was easily met, making the composite arm boom safe for manned flight use.

Fig. 15 — Test panel following flammability testing.

Manufacturing Phase

Arm Boom manufacturing follows the basic flow shown in Figure 16. Several areas of the fabrication process are critical to meeting the requirement for the arm booms.

The first of these critical fabrication steps is the layup of the basic structural tube. This task will be accomplished by supporting the tubular male production mold between spindles so that the mold may be rotated for convenient positioning of the graphite/epoxy tape. Rotating the tube will also allow simple application of the cross-plyed tapes. Figure 17 shows the layup for three 24-inch qualification test sections on the production mold. Three-inch GY-70/934 prepreg tape is used for ease of handling.

Fig. 16 – Arm boom manufacturing flow.

Fig. 17 – Graphite/epoxy three-inch prepreg tape is wrapped on a polished male aluminum mandrel for three qualification test sections.

The planar straightness of the cured structural tube will depend upon the straightness of the production mold during curing in the autoclave. To minimize warpage of the aluminum mold, several annealing/machining iterations were employed. The mold, during autoclave cure, is supported at its center and midpoint by an internal steel strongback. The strongback is supported at its ends so the vacuum bag material exterior to the tube is not abraded by supports. With the internal strongback in place and supported at its ends, the three support points inside the mold are vertically adjusted to remove the deflection of the mold. This approach ensures a straight mold when the tube is being cured in the autoclave.

Critical alignment of the tube ends will be accomplished on final assembly of the tube with its end fittings. An assembly fixture, Figure 18, will fix the tube end fittings in precise alignment while the end fittings are mechanically attached to the tube. An optical system using precision transits will be used. The tube will be supported vertically at its center of gravity. The assembly procedure will be closely monitored to ensure that built-in stresses during assembly are minimized. Final inspection of the end alignment will be done in an unrestrained free state.

Qualification Phase

Before starting qualification testing on full size booms, tests will be conducted on 24-inch, full diameter sections with production design end rings. These tests will verify strength and stability of the design with and without moderate damage. Figure 19 illustrates the test plan.

A rigorous test program will then follow to qualify and accept the first set of flight arm booms. Figure 20 shows the test cycle for the first set of qualification booms; subsequent flight booms will only be subjected to the acceptance portion of the cycle.

Non-Destructive Testing and Repair In-Service

The ultrasonic C-scan is the nondestructive testing (NDT) method for inspecting the arm tubes after fabrication and testing. After shipment and installation and after each Shuttle mission, a built-in nondestructive testing feature of the bumper shell damage protection system allows for a simple visual inspection of the tube bumper to detect hidden damage.

Ultrasonic inspection techniques have been established to nondestructively evaluate the quality of the arm boom wall construction during and after fabrication and testing by measuring the extent and distribution of disbond and void content areas. This ultrasonic inspection uses an immersion, pulse-reflection technique employing a

Fig. 18 —

Final assembly and alignment of the aluminum end attachment rings is accomplished in a stress-free state in this precision, optically aligned fixture.

Fig. 21 — Ultrasonic inspection uses an immersion pulse reflection technique.

Fig. 22 — The immersion tank and transducer driving mechanism were designed to allow rapid C-scan with the bumper installed.

If the impact is below the five foot-pounds energy design level, no repair is required. If the impact is greater, indicating probable structural damage to the tube laminate, a simple standard repair can be made.

The standard repair is to cut away the bumper shell at least one inch outside the damage zone, cut a hole through the tube wall, and remove the damaged laminate. Using a field repair kit, inner and outer patches and a plug can be bonded over the hole with a room-temperature setting adhesive. Finally, a new piece of bumper shell can be patched in place.

Fig. 23 – Damage inspection, NDT, evaluation, and repair after delivery.

Summary

A stiff, dimensionally stable, lightweight composite design for the remote manipulator system arm booms has evolved from careful analysis and from developmental testing. With an innovative protective bumper system, the resulting structure is rugged and promises to give years of trouble-free operation in space. This paper has presented the technology necessary to develop and fabricate large, lightweight, dimensionally stable manipulators for the Shuttle era in space.